

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of formic and oxalic acids by quinolinium bromochromate

Rupal Kumbhat, Vinita Sharma and Kalyan K. Banerji

Department of Chemistry, J. N. V. University, Jodhpur-342 005, India

E-mail : banerjikk@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-0291-2742977

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Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of formic and oxalic acids by quinolinium bromochromate (QBC) have been studied in DMSO. The main product of oxidation is carbon dioxide. The reaction is first order with respect to QBC. Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics were observed with respect to the reductants. The reaction is acid-catalysed and the acid dependence has the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$. The oxidation of α -deuterioformic acid (DFA) exhibits a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 5.30$ at 298 K). The reaction has been studied in nineteen different organic solvents and the solvent effect has been analysed using Taft's and Swain's multiparametric equations. The temperature dependence of the kinetic isotope effect indicates the presence of a symmetrical cyclic transition state in the rate-determining step. Suitable mechanisms have been proposed.

Halochromates have been used as mild and selective oxidizing reagents in synthetic organic chemistry¹⁻⁵. We have interested in the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of the oxidation by complexed Cr^{VI} species and several reports, including that of oxalic and formic acids have emanated from our laboratory⁶⁻⁸. It was observed that the oxidations by pyridinium fluorochromate (PFC) and pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC) presented different kinetic pictures. There seems to be no report on the oxidation aspects of organic acids by quinolinium bromochromate (QBC). Therefore, we report in this paper the kinetics of oxidation of oxalic and formic acids by QBC in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) as solvent. The mechanistic aspects are discussed. A suitable mechanism has also been proposed.

Results and discussion

The oxidation of organic acids leads to the formation of carbon dioxide. The stoichiometric determination indicated the following overall reactions :

QBC undergoes a two-electron change. This is in accord with our earlier observations with both QFC⁹ and PCC¹⁰.

Rate laws :

The reactions were found to be first order with respect to QBC. The reaction rate increases with an increase in [organic acid] but not linearly (Table 1). A plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of oxalic and formic acids by QBC at 298 K

10^3 [QBC] mol dm ⁻³	[Organic Acid] mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}} \text{ s}^{-1}$	
		Oxalic acid	Formic acid
1.00	0.10	21.9	2.90
1.00	0.20	27.8	4.55
1.00	0.40	32.1	6.35
1.00	0.60	33.9	7.31
1.00	0.80	35.0	7.91
1.00	1.00	35.5	8.32
1.00	1.50	36.3	8.94
1.00	3.00	37.2	9.66
2.00	0.20	28.4	4.86
4.00	0.20	27.2	4.15
6.00	0.20	28.0	4.45
8.00	0.20	27.6	4.10
1.00	0.20	28.2*	4.76*

* contained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

[organic acid] versus $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ is linear with an intercept on the rate ordinate. Thus the reactions exhibited Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to the organic acids. This indicates the following overall mechanism (3) and (4) and the rate law (5),

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 K[\text{QBC}] [\text{Organic acid}] / (1 + K[\text{Organic acid}]) \quad (5)$$

The dependence of the reaction rate on reductant concentration was studied at different temperatures and the values of K and k_2 were evaluated from the double reciprocal plots. The thermodynamic and activation parameters, at 298 K, were also calculated from the values of K and k_2 respectively, at four different temperatures (Tables 2 and 3).

Induced polymerization of acrylonitrile :

The oxidation of organic acids by QBC, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the rate (Table 1).

Effect of acidity :

The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen-ion dependence has the following form (Table 4),

$$k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+] \quad (6)$$

The values of a and b , for oxalic acid, are $2.07 \pm 0.09 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $8.03 \pm 0.14 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively ($r^2 = 0.9988$). The corresponding values for the oxidation of formic acid are $2.81 \pm 0.08 \times 10^{-4}$ and $10.5 \pm 0.14 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ ($r^2 = 0.9993$).

Kinetic isotope effect :

To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step, the oxidation of DFA was studied. The results recorded in Tables 2 and 3, showed that while the formation constant, K , for the ordinary and

Table 2. Formation constants and thermodynamic parameters of the organic acids-QBC complexes

Acid	K ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)				ΔH kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
OA	28.8	13.5	6.15	3.30	-58.0 ± 0.6	-165 ± 2	-8.9 ± 0.6
FA	4.95	3.82	2.91	2.28	-22.3 ± 0.2	-56 ± 1	-5.6 ± 0.2
DFA	5.52	4.35	3.46	2.58	-21.6 ± 0.7	-52 ± 2	-6.1 ± 0.6

Table 3. Rate constants and activation parameters of the oxidation of organic acids by QBC

Subst.	$10^4 k_2 / (\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$				ΔH^* kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^* J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	ΔG^* kJ mol ⁻¹
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
OA	18.4	38.1	75.7	153	51.1 ± 0.6	-120 ± 2	86.8 ± 0.5
FA	5.13	10.5	21.1	44.1	51.9 ± 0.9	-128 ± 2	90.0 ± 0.8
DFA	0.93	1.98	4.06	8.73	54.1 ± 0.9	-135 ± 3	94.1 ± 0.7
k_H/k_D	5.52	5.30	5.19	5.05			

Table 4. Dependence of reaction rate on hydrogen ion concentration [QBC] = 0.001 mol⁻¹ dm⁻³, [Acid] = 0.10 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 298 K

Acid	At (TsOH/mol dm ⁻³)					
	0.10	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80	1.00
OA	29.1	36.3	52.0	70.7	84.2	101
FA	3.85	4.90	6.96	9.33	11.2	13.3

deuteriated formic acids have almost identical values, the rate constant for the decomposition of the complex, k_2 , exhibited a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 5.30$ at 298 K).

Solvent effect :

The oxidation of formic acid was studied in 19 different organic solvents. The choice of solvents was limited due to the solubility of QBC and its reaction with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with the solvents chosen. The kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values of K and k_2 are recorded in Table 5.

Table 5. Formation constants and rate constants for the decomposition of formic acid-QBC complexes in different solvents at 298 K

Solvents	K 10 ⁵ k_2		Solvents	K 10 ⁵ k_2	
	dm ³ mol ⁻¹	s ⁻¹		dm ³ mol ⁻¹	s ⁻¹
Chloroform	4.27	36.3	Acetic acid	3.21	14.8
1,2-Dichloromethane	4.58	34.6	Cyclohexane	4.25	0.72
Dichloromethane	4.14	33.1	Toluene	4.66	7.08
DMSO	3.82	105	Acetophenone	3.67	37.2
Acetone	3.76	28.8	THF	3.49	13.5
DMF	4.06	50.1	<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	4.55	16.2
Butanone	4.88	21.4	1,4-Dioxane	4.23	12.3
Benzene	3.96	8.91	Carbon disulfide	4.58	3.24
Ethylacetate	3.54	10.2	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	3.88	7.59
Nitrobenzene	3.95	35.5			

The formation constant of the intermediate complex, K , did not vary much with the solvent but the rate constant, k_2 , exhibited much variation in values with different solvents.

The rate constants, k_2 , in eighteen solvents (CS₂ was not considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship (7) of Kamlet *et al.*¹¹,

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (7)$$

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, (the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities and β is the hydrogen bond donor acidity. A_0 is the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 12 have a value

of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of eqn. (7), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β are given below as equation (8)–(11),

$$\log k_2 = -4.03 + 1.81 (\pm 0.19)\pi^* + 0.15 (\pm 0.16)\beta + 0.30 (\pm 0.15)\alpha \quad (8)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8767; sd = 0.18; n = 18; \psi = 0.38$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.04 + 1.71 (\pm 0.20)\pi^* + 0.25 (\pm 0.17)\beta \quad (9)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8439; sd = 0.19; n = 18; \psi = 0.42$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.91 + 1.77 (\pm 0.21)\pi^* \quad (10)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8197; sd = 0.20; n = 18; \psi = 0.44$$

$$\log k_2 = -5.03 + 0.56 (\pm 0.38)\beta \quad (11)$$

$$r^2 = 0.1221; sd = 0.45; n = 18; \psi = 0.96$$

Here n is the number of data points and ψ is the Exner's statistical parameter¹².

Kamlet's¹¹ triparametric equation explains *ca.* 88% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's¹² criterion the correlation is not even satisfactory (*cf.* eqn. 8). The major contribution is of solvent polarity. It alone accounts for 82% of the data. Both β and α play relatively minor roles.

The data on solvent effect were also analyzed in terms of Swain's equation¹³ of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents also (12),

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (12)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. $(A + B)$ is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of equation (12), separately with A and B and with $(A + B)$,

$$\log k_2 = 1.31 (\pm 0.03) A + 1.70 (\pm 0.02) B - 3.64 \quad (13)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9982; sd = 0.02; n = 19; \psi = 0.04$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.07 (\pm 0.56) A - 3.09 \quad (14)$$

$$r^2 = 0.1758; sd = 0.45; n = 19; \psi = 0.93$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.60 (\pm 0.23) B - 3.83 \quad (15)$$

$$r^2 = 0.7365; sd = 0.26; n = 19; \psi = 0.53$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.57 (\pm 0.05) (A + B) - 3.74 \quad (16)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9814; sd = 0.02; n = 19; \psi = 0.04$$

The rates of decomposition of the complex in different solvents showed an excellent correlation in Swain's equation [*cf.* eqn. (13)] with the cation-solvating power playing the major role. In fact, the cation-solvation alone account for *ca.* 74% of the data. The correlation with the anion-solvat-

ing power was very poor. The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$, also accounted for *ca.* 98% of the data. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 98% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of \log (rate) against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.6117$; $sd = 0.31$; $\psi = 0.64$).

Mechanism :

The presence of a substantial kinetic isotopic effect confirmed that an $-C-H$ bond is cleaved in the rate-determining step. The observed kinetics indicate the formation of an intermediate complex in a rapid pre-equilibrium. However, the highly unfavourable entropy term obtained in the complex formation of oxalic acid-QBC reaction suggests that oxalic acid acts as a bidentate ligand and forms a cyclic intermediate complex. In the chromic acid oxidation also, the formation of a cyclic anhydride intermediate, oxalyl chromate, has been postulated¹⁴. The value of formation constant, $9.5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, reported by Hassan and Rocek¹⁴ compares favourably with the values obtained in this investigation. The absence of any effect of a radical scavenger, acrylonitrile, indicates that a hydrogen abstraction mechanism, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely.

For the formic acid oxidation, the cation-solvating power of the solvents plays a relatively more important role. Therefore, formation of an electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state is indicated. Thus the decomposition of QBC-formic acid complex may involve a hydride ion transfer via an anhydride intermediate (Scheme 1).

The involvement of a concerted cyclic process is supported by a study of the temperature dependence of the kinetic isotope effect¹⁵. The data for protio- and deuterio-formic acids when fitted in the familiar expression $k_H/k_D = A_H A_D \exp(-\Delta H^*/RT)$ show a direct correspondence with the properties of a symmetrically transition state in which the differences in the activation energies for the protio and deuterio compounds are equal to the differences in the zero point energies of the corresponding C-H and C-D bonds (ca. 4.5 kJ mol⁻¹) and the entropies of the activation of the respective reactions are almost equal^{16,17}.

The observed dependence on the hydrogen-ion concentration in both the reactions shows there to be an additional acid-catalysed pathway. This may be attributed to a rapid reversible protonation of the anhydride, with the protonated anhydride decomposing at a rate higher than the decomposition of the unprotonated anhydride (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

In the oxidation of these acids by QBC, PFC⁶ and PBC⁸ Michaelis-Menten type kinetics, with respect to the reductants, were obtained, but with PCC⁷ the reactions are of first order with respect to the reductants. It is possible that the values of the formation constants for the reductant-PCC complexes are very low. This resulted in the observation of second-order kinetics. No explanation of the difference is available presently. Kinetic isotope effects, solvent effects and the dependence of the hydrogen ions are of similar nature in all these reactions, for which essentially similar mechanisms have been proposed.

Experimental

QBC and α -deuterioformic acid (DCO₂H or DFA) were prepared by the reported methods^{5,18}. Due to the non-aqueous nature of the medium, toluene-*p*-sulfonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. TsOH is a strong acid and in a polar solvent like DMSO it is likely to be completely ionised. Solvents were purified by the usual methods¹⁹.

To determine the stoichiometry, an excess of QBC ($\times 5$ or greater) was reacted with the organic acid in DMSO (100 cm³) and the amount of residual QBC after the completion

of reaction was measured spectrophotometrically at 365 nm. The results indicated 1 : 1 stoichiometry. No quantitative determination of carbon dioxide formed was carried out.

The oxidation state of chromium in completely reduced reaction mixtures, determined by an iodometric method, was 3.95 ± 0.2 .

Kinetic measurements :

The reactions were followed under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping a large excess ($\times 15$ or greater) of the organic acid over QBC. the temperature was kept constant to ± 0.1 K. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of QBC spectrophotometrically at 365 nm for up to 80% of the reaction. No other reactant or product has any significant absorption at this wavelength. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} , were evaluated from the linear ($r = 0.995-0.999$) plots of $\log [\text{QBC}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$.

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